

PHARMACOKINETIC AND PHARMACODYNAMIC COMPARISON BETWEEN NOVEL SUSTAINED RELEASE VS CONVENTIONAL DYDROGESTERONE USED IN PREGNANCY WITH THE HELP OF SCINTIGRAPHY (EPSAR STUDY)

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To compare the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of once-daily sustained-release (SR) dydrogesterone 20 mg with twice-daily conventional dydrogesterone 10 mg in a rabbit model.

Methods: Technetium-99m scintigraphy tracked in vivo disintegration of radiolabeled tablets, and serial blood sampling determined pharmacokinetic parameters. For efficacy, pregnant rabbits received SR dydrogesterone 2 mg once daily from mating through the first trimester, followed by post-treatment ultrasonography, biochemical assays (PIBF, integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$, VEGF), and endometrial histopathology; comparators were conventional dydrogesterone and saline control.

Results: Scintigraphy revealed prolonged disintegration and sustained drug release from SR dydrogesterone. The two-fold higher t_{max} (6 h) of SR dydrogesterone compared to conventional (3 h), confirmed the

sustained release behavior. SR dydrogesterone (34.8 ± 5.1 ng.h/mL) demonstrated nearly 2-fold higher AUC_{0-48} compared to conventional dydrogesterone (14.4 ± 2.8 ng.h/mL), however at same dose AUC_{0-48} were comparable. ER scores of ultrasound assessment, level of

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progesterone-induced blocking factor (PIBF), and integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$ was not significantly different among both the treatments, but were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than control. Interestingly, level of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) was statistically higher for SR dydrogesterone compared to conventional dydrogesterone ($p < 0.05$) and control ($p < 0.001$). Endometrium of animals treated with SR dydrogesterone showed dense vasculature compared to moderate for conventional dydrogesterone and low for control group animals. Both the treatments were found to be safe and no changes in endometrial glands, lining, shape and other microstructures were observed post-treatment. **Conclusion:** Once-daily SR dydrogesterone 20 mg is comparable to twice-daily conventional dydrogesterone 10 mg in kinetics and in enhancing endometrial receptivity during first trimester.

KEYWORDS: Dydrogesterone, Endometrial receptivity, Pharmacokinetics, Scintigraphy, Sustained release.

INTRODUCTION

Oral progesterone is a proven and effective treatment for several uterine disorders.^[1] However, hepatic first-pass metabolism and low oral bioavailability (<10 %) have limited its widespread use.^[2] Dydrogesterone, a synthetic stereoisomer of the natural progesterone, is considered an alternative to oral progesterone.^[3-5] Dydrogesterone, owing its unique pharmacological features, offers increased affinity for progesterone receptors, decreased affinity for steroid receptors, and improved bioavailability compared to oral progesterone.^[3]

In recent years, dydrogesterone has been widely used in gynecology and obstetrics for the treatment of varied conditions such as irregular menstruation,^[6] dysmenorrhea,^[7] threatened or recurrent miscarriage^[8] and as a vital component of menopausal hormone therapy.^[9] Besides, multiple doses of conventional dydrogesterone tablets are also recommended for polycystic ovarian syndrome,^[10] abortion,^[8] infertility,^[3] and endometriosis.^[11] Dydrogesterone is effective in preventing miscarriages by sustaining a healthy womb lining and promoting endometrial receptivity.^[12] According to a recent survey, dydrogesterone 10 mg twice daily and/ or 10 mg thrice daily for a duration ranging from a few weeks to a few months was the most recommended schedule by the gynecologists.^[13] Multiple doses of conventional dydrogesterone for long duration raise concerns of low adherence and poor patient compliance.^[14] Adherence to dydrogesterone treatment is vital for achieving positive pregnancy outcomes, especially in cases of luteal phase defects, threatened miscarriage, and recurrent pregnancy loss.^[15] Reports indicate that nonadherence to long-term treatment is a

stern problem, accounting for more than 50% of cases where therapeutic goals are not achieved.^[16,17] The adherence problems further exaggerate when self-administration is required, as in the case of dydrogesterone treatment. Several existing reports suggested that reducing dosage frequency from twice daily to once daily dosing may improve adherence to therapies among patients and subsequent decreases in health care costs.^[18] Thus, several attempts have been made to develop sustained-release (SR) dydrogesterone dosage forms.^[14,19,20] The SR dydrogesterone is expected to provide better therapeutic compliance and treatment adherence, thus providing better clinical results. In a recent clinical study, the SR dydrogesterone tablet is bioequivalent to the conventional dydrogesterone tablet.^[19] The present study aimed at evaluating the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of once-daily, SR dydrogesterone (20 mg) in comparison to twice-daily, conventional dydrogesterone (10 mg), in rabbits. In vivo scintigraphy imaging, following oral administration of technetium-99m (^{99m}Tc) radiolabeled formulations, was conducted to evaluate the SR behavior. Plasma dydrogesterone was determined at predesignated time points for kinetics. For dynamics, pregnant rabbits were used, and endometrial changes were determined using ultrasonography, biochemical changes, and endometrial histopathology post-treatment. Comparison was made against conventional dydrogesterone and animals treated with saline (control).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials

Dydrogesterone SR tablet (Dydrohope 20 mg, Corona Remedies) and conventional tablets (Duphaston 10 mg, Abbott) were purchased from a local pharmacy shop (Kamla Nagar, New Delhi). The stannous chloride was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO), and ^{99m}Tc was obtained from Baba Atomic Research Centre (Mumbai, India). All other chemicals used were of analytical grade and were purchased from CDH Laboratory (New Delhi, India). A scintigraphy study was conducted at Batra Research Center (New Delhi, India).

Experimental animals

Adult female New Zealand White rabbits, 4 to 6 months old, weighing 2.0 to 4.5 kg were used. The rabbits were housed in a controlled environment with $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ temperature, $57 \pm 7\%$ relative humidity, a 12-hour light/dark cycle with standard hygienic conditions, free access to fresh tap water, and ad libitum a pelleted diet. All animal experiment was performed

as per the guidelines of the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals and with the approved protocol (RRI/IAEC/2024/02) of Rodent Research India, Haryana. The animals were acclimatized for two weeks before the experiment.

Scintigraphy and pharmacokinetics

Scintigraphy and pharmacokinetic study were conducted in non-pregnant rabbits (n=6). Rabbits were randomly divided into two groups (n=6). One group received conventional dydrogesterone (10 mg tablet) formulation (CDF group) and the other received SR dydrogesterone (20 mg tablet) formulation (SDF group). For scintigraphy, the tablets were radiolabeled with ^{99m}Tc using the drill and fill method as described previously.^[21] Briefly, a hole in the centre of the tablet was made with the help of a needle and filled with stannous chloride reduced per technetate. The remaining space of the hole was filled with lactose and completely sealed with wax. The radioactive counts of the tablets were determined using a dose calibrator (PTW Curiementor 2, USA). Labeling efficiency and stability were confirmed by instant thin-layer chromatography. Radiolabeling was conducted carefully so that each tablet should have nearly 2 MBq of radioactivity. Similarity in dissolution profile of radiolabeled and non-radiolabeled study product validated that the radiolabeling had no impact on dispersion behavior. Radiolabeled tablets were orally administered to animals with a feeding sonde such that the tablet was placed close to the esophagus, avoiding chewing and crushing. Sequential scintigraphic images and blood samples were collected at predesignated time points. Scintigraphy images of the abdominal area were captured with dual dual-head SPECT gamma camera (Millennium MG, GE Healthcare, US) until complete disintegration of the tablet occurred. The images were analyzed using the Genie 4.5 image analysis. Blood samples were collected from the marginal ear vein using a syringe. The plasma was separated, extracted with methanol and the drug content was determined by a developed LC-MS/MS method.^[22] All the samples were stored at -20°C until analyzed.

Pharmacodynamics

For efficacy, 18 female rabbits were randomly divided into 3 groups (n=6): (a) control group treated with 1 ml normal saline twice-daily, (b) CDF group treated with conventional dydrogesterone (1 mg) twice-daily and, (c) SDF group treated with SR dydrogesterone granules (2 mg) once-daily. The pregnancy was induced by mating with male rabbits. The treatment begins with the mating and lasts till the end of the first trimester (11-13 days), determined through palpation. The formulations were dispersed in water and fed through an

oral sonde, directly into the esophagus. All the evaluations were made post-treatment, at the end of the first trimester.

Ultrasound Assessment

Each animal was properly restrained physically and placed on dorsal recumbency. Hair from the abdomen was gently made wet, with a soaked cotton in water and shaved. The shaved region was cleaned thoroughly with a dry cotton and swabbed with wool soaked in an antiseptic solution. Ultrasound gel was then applied to the shaved area, and ultrasonography was conducted using an ultrasound machine. A transcutaneous probe was used to scan the abdomino-pelvic region. The probe was placed gently on the skin and tilted until a descriptive echographic image was obtained. Endometrial receptivity was assessed by considering the endometrial thickness (distance from the interface between the endometrium and myometrium), volume, contraction or peristalsis and blood flow of the endometrium.^[23] We assessed endometrial receptivity by considering the modified endometrial receptivity (ER) scoring system as described previously^[22] and shown in Table 1. All the ultrasound parameters were examined by the same doctor using the same ultrasound instrument.

Table 1: Representative endometrial receptivity (ER) scores.

Parameters	Score 0	Score 1	Score 2
Endometrial thickness	< 7 mm	7-10 mm	10-14 mm
Endometrial layering	Absent	Hazy	Distinct
Endometrial echogenic line	Heterogenous	Homogenous	-
Endometrial volume	< 3 ml	> 3 ml	-
Endometrial blood flow	Absent	Sparse	Multifocal

Biochemical Analysis

Blood samples (1 ml) were collected from the marginal ear vein of each animal using a syringe. The samples were collected in heparinized tubes and centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 20 minutes to get plasma. Samples were stored at -20°C until hormonal analyses. We assayed progesterone-induced blocking factor (PIBF), integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$ and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) using ELISA kits (Krishgen, India) as per manufacturer's protocol. The PIBF, integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$ and VEGF were expressed in nanomoles per liter, nanograms per milliliter and picograms per milliliter, respectively.

Endometrial Histopathology

The change in morphology of the endometrium due to dydrogesterone treatment was evaluated using histopathology. Briefly, post-treatment, the animals were euthanized by

intraperitoneal injection of sodium barbital. The abdominal wall was opened longitudinally along the midline, the uterus was excised, and the entire endometrium was peeled off the uterus. The endometrial tissue was fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, embedded in paraffin, and cut into 4-5 μm -thick sections. The samples were then stained with hematoxylin-eosin for assessment of morphological changes. Sections were observed under a light microscope (Olympus) at 400x of original magnification. Ten visual fields were analyzed per tissue section from each animal.

Statistical Analysis

All the data were presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Comparison of groups was done using the one-way ANOVA. The $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. All statistical calculations were done using SPSS V26.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Scintigraphy and pharmacokinetics

Fig. 1 illustrates scintigraphic images of the CDF and SDF group animals administered with conventional and SR dydrogesterone tablets, respectively. The scintigraphy images showed a distinct in vivo release pattern for conventional and SR tablets. Conventional dydrogesterone tablets (CDF group) remained intact for up to 1 h and disintegrated in the duodenum or upper intestine within 2 h. Complete disintegration of the conventional tablet occurred within 4 h in the small intestine (Fig. 1). In contrast, SR tablets remained intact for up to 6 h. Images showed a small fraction of drug release, possibly due to polymer erosion from the tablet surface. Further, the tablet disintegrated in the small intestine at 8 h, followed by drug release. As expected, scintigraphy revealed prolonged disintegration and slow drug release from the SR formulation.

Figure 1: Scintigraphy images depicting disintegration of (A) Conventional dydrogesterone and (B) SR dydrogesterone at different time points following oral delivery to rabbits.

Fig. 2 depicts the plot of dydrogesterone plasma concentration as a function of time post-administration of conventional and SR dydrogesterone. The relevant pharmacokinetic parameters are listed in Table 2. The pharmacokinetic results were in corroboration with scintigraphy findings, and SR dydrogesterone showed nearly 2.4-fold higher AUC_{0-48} compared to the conventional formulation. As expected, the t_{max} of SR dydrogesterone was twice (6 h) that of conventional dydrogesterone (3 h). Additionally, the C_{max} of the SR dydrogesterone was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than conventional dydrogesterone. The mean resident time of conventional dydrogesterone (9.06) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than SR dydrogesterone (18.8). Also, the fluctuation index for SR dydrogesterone was 2.18, which was markedly lower than the fluctuation index of conventional dydrogesterone (3.42). The kinetic data confirmed the prolonged release behavior and consistent drug concentration in the plasma of SR dydrogesterone.

Figure 2: Plot of dydrogesterone concentration in plasma as a function of time following oral administration of conventional and SR dydrogesterone to rabbits (n=6).

Table 2: Pharmacokinetic parameters of CDF and SDF group rabbits (n=6).

Parameter	CDF group	SDF group
C_{max} (ng/ml)	2.68 ± 0.18	$2.08 \pm 0.08^*$
t_{max} (h)	3 h	6 h*
AUC_{0-48} (ng.h/ml)	14.4 ± 2.8	$34.8 \pm 5.1^*$
MRT (h)	9.06	18.8*
Fluctuation Index	3.42	2.18

* $p < 0.05$ vs CDF

Ultrasound Assessment

No significant difference in dose duration exists between the groups and the dose duration was 11.83 ± 0.83 , 12.17 ± 0.75 and 12.0 ± 0.63 days for SDF, CDF and the control group, respectively. When comparing the ultrasound parameters of endometrial receptivity between the control and treatment groups, it was found that the mean endometrial thickness for the control group (9.77 ± 0.46 mm) was significantly less ($p < 0.05$) than the treatment group. The mean endometrial thickness for the CDF and SDF group animals was 11.9 ± 0.28 mm and 12.07 ± 0.20 mm, respectively (Table 3), and the difference was not statistically significant. In the control group, 2 out of 6 animals showed distinct endometrial layering, 2 showed hazy layering and in the remaining 2 the layering was absent. Four out of six animals in both the CDF and SDF groups showed distinct endometrial layering. Further, both the remaining animals in the SDF group have hazy layering, unlike the CDF group, where layering was absent in one animal (Table 3).

Table 3: Sonographic observations of individual rabbits for all three groups (n=6).

Parameters	Sonographic observations in Rabbit					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>Endometrial thickness</i>						
Control	9.7	9.9	10.2	9.8	10.1	8.9
CDF	12.2	11.8	11.7	12.3	11.6	11.8
SDF	12.3	12.2	11.8	12.0	11.9	12.2
<i>Endometrial layering</i>						
Control	Distinct	Distinct	Hazy	Hazy	Absent	Absent
CDF	Distinct	Distinct	Distinct	Distinct	Hazy	Absent
SDF	Distinct	Distinct	Distinct	Distinct	Hazy	Hazy
<i>Endometrial echogenic line</i>						
Control	Homo	Homo	Homo	Homo	Hetero	Hetero
CDF	Homo	Homo	Homo	Homo	Homo	Hetero
SDF	Homo	Homo	Homo	Homo	Homo	Homo
<i>Endometrial volume</i>						
Control	> 3	> 3	> 3	> 3	< 3	< 3
CDF	> 3	> 3	> 3	> 3	> 3	< 3
SDF	> 3	> 3	> 3	> 3	> 3	< 3
<i>Endometrial blood flow</i>						
Control	Sparse	Sparse	Sparse	Sparse	Sparse	Sparse
CDF	Multifocal	Multifocal	Multifocal	Sparse	Sparse	Absent
SDF	Multifocal	Multifocal	Multifocal	Sparse	Sparse	Sparse

The endometrial echogenic line results were in agreement with endometrial layering. Homogenous echogenic line was observed in 4 control animals, 5 CDF group animals and in all 6 SDF group animals. Similarly, endometrial volume greater than 3 ml was observed in 4 out of 6 control animals and in 5 out of 6 animals in both treatments. Three out of six CDF and SDF group animals showed multifocal blood flow. Further, 2 CDF group animals showed sparse blood flow, and in the last one, the blood flow was not visible. In contrast, all the remaining 3 SDF group animals showed sparse blood flow. Interestingly, none of the control animals showed multifocal blood flow, and all showed sparse blood flow (Table 3). The representative ultrasonographic image of one animal from each group is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Representative ultrasonography image of control, CDF and SDF group rabbit at the end of first trimester (A) endometrial image and (B) endometrial blood flow.

Consequently, the ER score for each animal of the control and treatment groups is shown in Table 4. ER score of the treatment groups was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than control (4.67). The higher ER score of treated animals correlates with improved clinical pregnancy rates and demonstrates the effectiveness of dydrogesterone in endometrial receptivity. Among treatment groups, SDF showed a higher ER score (7.0) than the CDF group (6.5), but the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4: Table representing ER scores for various groups.

Parameters	ER Scores (n=6)		
	Control group	CDF group	SDF group
Endometrial thickness	8	12	12
Endometrial layering	6	9	10
Endometrial echogenic line	4	5	6
Endometrial volume	4	5	5
Endometrial blood flow	6	8	9
Total score	28	39	42
Mean Score	4.67	6.5	7.0

Biochemical analysis

The endometrial receptivity can be predicted by biochemical assessment of markers such as VEGF, integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$, and PIBF. Results (Fig. 4) showed that all three biochemicals are positively correlated with dydrogesterone treatment. Improved levels of VEGF, integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$, and PIBF were observed in treatment groups compared to control ($p < 0.05$). The level of PIBF and integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$ was not significantly different among treatment groups. However, the VEGF level of SDF animals was statistically higher ($p < 0.05$) than CDF animals.

Figure 4: Plasma level of (A) PIBF, (B) Integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$, and (C) VEGF in control, CDF and SDF animals. Bar represents standard deviation.

* $p < 0.001$ vs control and # $p < 0.05$ vs CDF.

Endometrial histopathology

Histopathology images of the endometrium of control, CDF and SDF group animals are shown in Fig. 5. No changes in endometrial glands, lining, shape, and other microstructures of treatment group animals were observed and images were similar to control animals.

Glands are lined by oval to elongated cells having oval nuclei with coarse chromatin and conspicuous nucleoli. Further, the gland-to-stromal ratio was also maintained in the treatment group, similar to control. The glandular response was better in the treatment groups compared to the control and the score was 2 for the treatment group and 1 for the control. We observed that the three groups differ in vasculature (Fig. 5). The Control group showed few blood vessels, whereas animals treated with dydrogesterone showed moderate to dense vasculature. In both the treatment groups, the blood vessels were scattered and the majority were seen at the junction of endometrium and myometrium (Fig. 5). The vascularity score was 1, 2, and 3 for control, CDF and SDF group animals, respectively. The SDF group showed better vascularity compared to the other two groups. The results showed that these effects could be due to dydrogesterone, which showed pregestational effects mimicking the luteal phase.

Figure 5: Endometrium histopathology of (A) Control, (B) CDF and (C) SDF group animals. Red arrow: glands; blue arrow: blood vessels; and green arrow: stroma's.

DISCUSSION

The preclinical assessments of the present study demonstrated pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic equivalence of once-daily SR dydrogesterone and twice-daily conventional dydrogesterone with respect to bioavailability and endometrial receptivity, foreseeing SR dydrogesterone as a valuable, patient-compliant alternative to conventional dydrogesterone, particularly for chronic reproductive disorders such as luteal phase defects, threatened miscarriage, and recurrent pregnancy loss requiring long-term treatment.^[14] Adherence to dydrogesterone treatment is vital for achieving positive pregnancy outcomes, and formulation with reduced dosage frequency is expected to improve adherence and patient compliance.^[15] Tc-99m scintigraphy, along with kinetics, was used to assess the in vivo performance of the radiolabeled formulations. Our kinetic data showed 2-fold higher t_{max} and significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower C_{max} of SR dydrogesterone compared to conventional dydrogesterone. The results were consistent with scintigraphy and SR formulation demonstrated delayed disintegration (\square 8 h) in the small intestine compared to conventional dydrogesterone (\square 4 h), which completely disintegrated in the stomach or duodenum. In agreement, the mean resident time of SR dydrogesterone was nearly twice that of conventional dydrogesterone. The result suggested prolonged release behavior of SR dydrogesterone. The t_{max} of conventional dydrogesterone in our study was similar to a previous report.^[24]

It is expected that SR formulation allows at least a 2-fold reduction in dosage frequency compared to conventional formulation.^[25] Concordantly, SR dydrogesterone demonstrated 2.4-fold higher bioavailability (AUC_{0-48}) compared to conventional dydrogesterone. Notably, bioavailability was obtained after single-dose administration of 20 mg SR and 10 mg conventional dydrogesterone. The dose-normalized AUC showed that the SR dydrogesterone was bioequivalent to conventional dydrogesterone, though the former performed slightly better. The present findings were in corroboration with a recent phase III trial where extended-release dydrogesterone (20 mg) showed efficacy analogous to immediate-release dydrogesterone (10 mg).^[19] Further, our preclinical kinetic data were comparable, if not similar, to a recent clinical bioequivalence study by Sharma AD et al.^[24]

Importantly, the lower fluctuation index and higher mean resident time for SR dydrogesterone ensure more consistent concentrations of dydrogesterone in the systemic circulation over a prolonged period. Our scintigraphy and kinetic data provide clear evidence

that SR dydrogesterone (20 mg) is a viable once-daily alternative to twice-daily conventional dydrogesterone. Further, SR dydrogesterone with a simpler dosage regimen could improve adherence and patient compliance.^[16,17]

We compared efficacy following treatment of rabbits with either SR dydrogesterone (SDF group) or conventional dydrogesterone (CDF group). The comparison was also made with control rabbits treated with normal saline. The treatment duration was decided considering dydrogesterone use in the first trimester of pregnancy^[15,26] and the short gestation period (32 ± 1 day) of rabbits.^[27] Further, it is difficult to determine pregnancy in rabbits therefore, treatment started with the mating instead of pregnancy and the data showed that the mean dosing duration between the groups did not differ significantly. To evaluate the effect of dydrogesterone on endometrial receptivity, ultrasound assessment, biochemical analysis and histopathology were conducted.^[28-31] All the evaluations were done post-treatment at the end of the first trimester. The endometrial thickness, layering, echo, volume, and blood flow were assessed by ultrasonography, and ER scores were obtained for each animal. Significantly higher ER score and PIBF, integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$ and VEGF levels in both the treatment groups compared to control, provide substantial evidence for the role of dydrogesterone in improvement of endometrial receptivity.^[15] Higher ER scores generally indicate a more receptive endometrium, suggesting a higher probability of implantation.^[27] Similarly, PIBF prevents the embryo from immune attack and integrin $\alpha V\beta 3$, a cell adhesion molecule, helps in implantation.^[29] Notably, VEGF overexpression in first trimester, regulates the development of new blood vessels required for fetal growth.^[30] The similar dydrogesterone effects on endometrium and hormone levels were reported previously.^[15] Though the ER scores and biochemical pregnancy markers are significantly lower in the control group but all are within the normal range. This is expected, since we have used a normal pregnancy model and not the animal models of adverse pregnancy outcomes.^[32] Importantly, our results demonstrated that SR dydrogesterone is equally effective as conventional dydrogesterone except for VEGF levels, which were higher ($p < 0.05$) in SR dydrogesterone-treated animals. Additionally, the levels of all the pregnancy markers were within range and confirm the safety of dydrogesterone treatment.

In conformity, the cross-sectional image of the endometrium of SDF animals also showed dense blood vessels. Further, no cellular or morphological abnormality was observed in the endometrium of treated animals and the results were similar to control animals. The findings

clearly suggested that dydrogesterone is beneficial for implantation and that once-daily SR dydrogesterone treatment is equally, if not more, effective than twice-daily conventional dydrogesterone in enhancing endometrial receptivity during the first trimester.

Study limitations

Firstly, the studies were conducted in rabbits having a short gestation period (31 - 33 days), unlike humans with a long gestation period (9 months). Secondly, the treatment started with the initiation of mating, not with pregnancy, since it is difficult to determine pregnancy in rabbits. Lastly, the comparison was made with the control group, however, baseline values of the same animals were not considered.

CONCLUSION

Once-daily, SR dydrogesterone represents a significant advancement in the management of chronic reproductive diseases, especially endometriosis, luteal phase defects, threatened miscarriage, and recurrent pregnancy loss. SR dydrogesterone with reduced dose frequency would have better treatment adherence, thus providing better pregnancy outcomes. The more consistent blood levels achieved via SR dydrogesterone could lead to better symptom control and better clinical outcomes. The incorporation of SR technology into dydrogesterone therapy thus enhances its clinical utility, providing a convenient and effective solution for patients suffering from chronic reproductive diseases.

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STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

There is no financial or non-financial interests among authors that are directly or indirectly related to the work submitted for publication.

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